

Analysis and Diagnosis of Inter-Turn Short Circuit Faults in Dual Rotor Air-Cored PMSG - Series Connected Stator Coils

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Abstract—Inter-turn short circuit (ITSC) fault detection is a major challenge for direct-drive permanent magnet synchronous generators in renewable energy applications. In this paper, ITSC phenomena are investigated in a dual-rotor, air-cored Permanent Magnet Synchronous Generator (PMSG) with series-connected coils. An accurate finite element analysis model is developed and mathematically validated to characterize the electromagnetic performance under healthy and faulty conditions. In order to decipher the effect of ITSCs on the stator current distribution, contact resistance, and short-circuit ratio variations are investigated to derive the fault-induced current signatures. Typical conventional diagnostic methods like Motor Current Signature Analysis (MCSA) and Extended Park’s Vector Approach (EPVA) are evaluated and found to be less sensitive on low-severity faults, which may lead to misdiagnosis. These findings suggest the need for complementary monitoring strategies towards the early fault detection for better operation reliability and efficiency of renewable energy systems.

Index Terms—Fault diagnosis, Inter-turn short-circuit fault, Permanent magnet generators, Renewable energy.

I. INTRODUCTION

Modern renewable energy technologies have placed emphasis on energy generation systems that are efficient, reliable and low maintenance [1]. High efficiency, compact design and robust operation in harsh environments with low maintenance requirements have been the cornerstone of direct-drive permanent magnet synchronous generators (PMSGs) [2]. The lightweight and modular C-GEN generator design has been reported to be the best among them for tidal, wave, and wind energy applications [3]. That is largely due to its innovative air-cored/modular architecture that reduces the system mass and simplifies assembly, ensuring high efficiency and reliable

performance in harsh and variable conditions typical of marine renewable energy environments.

The renewable energy systems, especially those under variable and harsh conditions, such as tidal and wave energy harvesting, present a challenge for the electrical machine design. Studies like [3] and [4] show that robust, low-speed, high-torque generators are required to replace expensive gear systems while ensuring reliability in submerged or coastal operation. Advanced modeling and optimization techniques like those in [5] have led to robust wave converters and tidal turbines with high energy conversion efficiency.

In spite of such advances, electrical and mechanical faults in PMSGs are often the most critical failure modes. Among the electrical faults inter-turn short circuit (ITSC) faults are caused by insulation degradation between adjacent turns, which may induce localized heating, increased copper losses and progressive demagnetization of permanent magnets, as shown in [6] and [7]. These faults degrade the machine efficiency and increase the risk of catastrophic failure if left undetected. Problems of ITSC faults are a research priority in renewable energy applications where the operational reliability of electrical machines is critical. The relevant stator current harmonics for the fault in high numbers of poles of PM generators are, therefore, directly related to the number of poles and stator-concentrated windings [8] - [9].

Recently developed fault detection and diagnosis techniques may provide mitigation of ITSC faults [10]. Classical methods like motor current signature analysis (MCSA) have been widely applied for fault diagnosis. Even though effective in many cases, MCSA is limited in identifying faults, especially under dynamic operating conditions or when mechanical defects like bearing issues or eccentricity are present [11]. Also, another limitation is MCSA’s dependence on machine geometry for demagnetization detection [8]. Moderate techniques

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such as dq-axis current harmonic analysis [12] - [14], flux monitoring [15], and back-electromotive force estimation [16] are capable of providing improved diagnostic capabilities. Such methods exploit physical and electromagnetic characteristics to identify early fault signatures for proactive fault management. For instance, voltage demodulation techniques [17] and machine learning based models such as support vector machines (SVMs) [18] and convolutional neural networks (CNNs) [19] are very promising for fault classification and severity estimation in variable operating conditions [20].

Moreover, advanced finite element analysis (FEA) [21] - [22] and co-simulation techniques have allowed modeling of ITSC faults, including magnetic saturation, spatial harmonics, and thermal effects. Such strategies allow for deep insight into the electromagnetic as well as thermal behavior of faulty machines for designing robust fault-tolerant control strategies [23]. Besides, real-time monitoring techniques, such as the residual insulation capacity estimation and adaptive linear neuron (Adaline) algorithms for harmonic extraction improve the accuracy and responsiveness of ITSC fault detection.

The different and harsh operation conditions of renewable energy systems demand fault tolerant designs and efficient diagnostic approaches.. In this paper, ITSC fault analysis and management for radial C-GEN generator design are reviewed based on the prior researches on demagnetization and fault diagnosis in PMSGs [6] - [7]. With advanced modeling, mathematical validation and diagnostic techniques this work presents insights into ITSC fault progression, detection and mitigation strategies. They seek to improve the reliability and operational efficiency of renewable energy systems and further establish the role of direct-drive PMSGs for the transition towards sustainable energy solutions.

II. FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS (FEA) MODEL DEVELOPMENT

A model of an axial flux C-GEN generator has been built and developed via FEA software, then its performance is compared with the experimental results of real devices aiming for a reliable electromagnetic analysis. A cross section of the model is depicted in Fig.1 together with the distribution of the magnetic flux under healthy conditions. The nominal characteristics of the generator and the comparative results of the FEA model with that of the experimental testing are listed in Tables I, II along, with the percentile difference between the two. The simulated machine represents the real one with accuracy.

Table I: FEA Verification

	FEA	Experimental	Deviation(%)
Phase Voltage(V)	222.4	217.5	2.24
Phase Current(A)	12.02	12.4	3.08
Torque(Nm)	1145.5	1067	7
Electrical Power(kW)	8023	8069	0.56
Mechanical Power(kW)	9500	8938	6
Efficiency(%)	85.3	90.28	3.28

Figure 1: 3D-FEA model of the axial C-GEN generator

Table II: Generator Properties

Rated Power(kW)	8
Rated Speed(rpm)	80
Stator	Coreless
Frequency(Hz)	32
Pole pairs	24
Stator Coils	36 x single concentrated
Stator Coil turns	90
Magnet material	N42

III. CURRENT ANALYSIS

A. Mathematical Analysis

The equivalent circuit of the axial flux C-GEN PMSG is shown in Fig.2. For this analysis, only the phase containing the ITSC will be studied, resulting in the equivalent circuit presented in Fig.3. In this study, the goal is to understand the effects of ITSC in the C-GEN. Therefore, a steady-state analysis will be conducted. E_c represents the EMF of each coil, E_f represents the EMF of the faulty coil and E_h the EMF of the healthy coil. The parameter k denotes the number of series-connected coils per phase, while n is the harmonic order. The rotational speed is represented by ω and stands for the rotational speed, while the short-circuit ratio is given by $\mu = \frac{N_{\text{shorted}}}{N_{\text{total}}}$, where N represents the number of turns per coil. The contact resistance is denoted by R_{cont} . The coil resistances are defined as follows: R_h for the healthy part of the shorted coil, R_f for the shorted coil, and R_c for a coil without ITSC. Similarly, the inductances are represented as L_h for the healthy part of the shorted coil, L_f for the shorted coil, and L_c for a coil without ITSC.

Due to the strength of the magnets and the lack of an iron core, it can be assumed that $E_f = \mu \cdot E_c$ and $E_h = (1 - \mu) \cdot E_c$.

Figure 2: Equivalent Circuit under ITCS

Figure 3: Simplified equivalent circuit under ITCS

Figure 4: Steady-state simplified equivalent circuit under ITCS

Similarly, the resistance of the coil can be expressed as $R_f = \mu \cdot R_c$ and $R_h = (1 - \mu) \cdot R_c$. The previous assumptions are not valid for the coil inductance, as the ITSC induces a mutual inductance, which must be taken into account; therefore, the steady-state analysis will be performed based on the equivalent circuit shown in Fig. 4. The mutual inductance M is given by $M = (k - \mu) \cdot \mu \cdot P$, where P represents the permeance. The coil and load impedance are given as $Z_c = R_c + j \cdot n \cdot \omega \cdot L_c$ and $Z_{Load} = R_{Load} + j \cdot n \cdot \omega \cdot L_{Load}$ respectively. For the equivalent circuit shown in Fig.4, a mesh current analysis will be performed, while the effect of the mutual inductance will be modeled as $\Delta(\mu) = j \cdot n \cdot \omega \cdot M$. The resulting steady-state equations are given in eq.1 and eq.2.

$$I_a \cdot [(k - \mu) \cdot Z_c + Z_{Load} + R_{cont}] + I_f \cdot [-R_{cont} - \Delta(\mu)] = (k - \mu) \cdot E_c \quad (1)$$

$$I_a \cdot [-R_{cont} + \Delta(\mu)] + I_f \cdot [\mu \cdot Z_c + R_{cont}] = \mu \cdot E_c \quad (2)$$

Solving with respect to I_a and I_f , eq.3 and eq.4 are obtained.

$$I_a = \frac{E_c \cdot [k \cdot R_{cont} + (k - \mu) \cdot \mu \cdot Z_c + \mu \cdot \Delta(\mu)]}{R_{cont} \cdot (k \cdot Z_c + Z_{Load}) + (k - \mu) \cdot \mu \cdot Z_c^2 + \mu \cdot Z_c \cdot Z_{Load} - \Delta^2(\mu)} \quad (3)$$

$$I_f = \frac{E_c \cdot [k \cdot R_{cont} + (k - \mu) \cdot \mu \cdot Z_c + \mu \cdot Z_{Load} - (k - \mu) \cdot \Delta(\mu)]}{R_{cont} \cdot (k \cdot Z_c + Z_{Load}) + (k - \mu) \cdot \mu \cdot Z_c^2 + \mu \cdot Z_c \cdot Z_{Load} - \Delta^2(\mu)} \quad (4)$$

To analyze the evolution of each current with respect to ITSC severity, the currents of phase A and the shorted coil will be differentiated with respect to contact resistance and the short-circuit ratio, and the effect of the mutual inductance will be neglected from the analysis for simplicity reasons and will be separately discussed. The currents of the coils will be differentiated with respect to contact resistance, as shown in the Appendix eq.9. The resulting expressions are given in eq.5 and 6 for the phase A of the faulty coil, respectively.

$$\frac{dI_a}{dR_{cont}} = \frac{E_c \cdot \mu^2 \cdot Z_c \cdot Z_{Load}}{[R_{cont} \cdot (k \cdot Z_c + Z_{Load}) + (k - \mu) \cdot \mu \cdot Z_c^2 + \mu \cdot Z_c \cdot Z_{Load}]^2} \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{dI_f}{dR_{cont}} = \frac{-E_c \cdot (k - \mu) \cdot \mu \cdot Z_c \cdot Z_{Load} - \mu \cdot Z_{Load}^2}{[R_{cont} \cdot (k \cdot Z_c + Z_{Load}) + (k - \mu) \cdot \mu \cdot Z_c^2 + \mu \cdot Z_c \cdot Z_{Load}]^2} \quad (6)$$

For phase A, the derivative is positive, indicating that while the contact resistance decreases, the current in the healthy coil will also decrease. For the shorted coil, a reduction in contact resistance leads to an increase in the current because the derivative is negative.

Differentiating with respect to the short-circuit ratio, as shown in the Appendix eq.10, results in eq.7 for the current of phase A and eq.8 for the shorted coil.

$$\frac{dI_a}{d\mu} = \frac{E_c \cdot [-\mu^2 \cdot Z_c^2 \cdot Z_{Load} - 2 \cdot \mu \cdot Z_c \cdot R_{cont} \cdot Z_{Load}]}{[R_{cont} \cdot (k \cdot Z_c + Z_{Load}) + (k - \mu) \cdot \mu \cdot Z_c^2 + \mu \cdot Z_c \cdot Z_{Load}]^2} \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{dI_f}{d\mu} = \frac{E_c \cdot [(k - 2 \cdot \mu) \cdot Z_c \cdot R_{cont} \cdot Z_{Load} + R_{cont} \cdot Z_{Load}^2]}{[R_{cont} \cdot (k \cdot Z_c + Z_{Load}) + (k - \mu) \cdot \mu \cdot Z_c^2 + \mu \cdot Z_c \cdot Z_{Load}]^2} \quad (8)$$

For phase A, it is evident that the derivative is negative, indicating that as the number of shorted turns increases, the current in phase A decreases. Similarly, for the shorted coil, the derivative is positive, which means that the current increases as the severity of the fault increases. A very important observation is that if the contact resistance is zero, the derivative of eq.8 is also zero; this means that the current of the shorted coil I_f only depends on their complex resistance.

In the previous analysis, the effect of mutual inductance was neglected. Since C-GEN is a low-speed air-cored generator, mutual inductance is relatively low, and its impact is further limited by the low operating frequency. Nonetheless, the multiplication of the corresponding current by mutual inductance is represented as a dependent source. In phase A, it is modeled as $-j \cdot n \cdot \omega \cdot M \cdot I_f$, while in the shorted coil, it is modeled as $j \cdot n \cdot \omega \cdot M \cdot I_a$. When the contact resistance decreases, the mutual inductance remains unchanged; therefore, its effect will result solely from the variations in current. For the loop of phase A, given in eq.1, the dependent source will be added to the EMF of phase A. I_f increases as the contact resistance R_{cont} decreases, leading to an increase of the current of phase A. Compared with eq.5, where it was found that I_a decreases with the decrease of the contact resistance, this will slow down the rate at

which the current decreases. For the loop of the shorted coil, given in eq.2, the multiplication of the corresponding current by mutual inductance will be subtracted from the EMF of the shorted coil. I_a decreases as the contact resistance R_{cont} decreases, leading to an increase of the current of the shorted coil I_f . Combined with eq.6, it will boost the rate which the current of the shorted coil increases. As the number of the shorted turns increases, the mutual inductance also increases. In the loop of phase A, given in eq.1, the multiplication of the corresponding current by mutual inductance will be added to the EMF of phase A. As the number of the shorted turns increases, the mutual inductance also increases, therefore the current of phase A will increase as the number of shorted turns increases. This effect will slow down the rate at which the current decreases observed in eq.7. In the loop of the shorted coil given in eq.2, the multiplication of the corresponding current by mutual inductance will be subtracted from the EMF of the shorted coil. As the number of shorted turns increases, the mutual inductance also increases, leading to a decrease in the shorted coil current I_f . This effect will slow down the rate at which the current increases found in eq.8. In the case where the contact resistance is zero, meaning the short circuit is ideal, the derivative found in eq.8 equals zero. This indicates that the effect of mutual inductance become significant. Therefore, when the ITSC is ideal, the current in the shorted coil will decrease.

In summary, the current of phase A decreases with the increase of the fault severity, and the current of the shorted coil increases with the increase of the fault severity with the exception of the contact resistance being zero, in which case the current will decrease. The effect of the mutual inductances are not significant as a result of the low frequency and the small permeance due to the air-cored stator.

B. Simulation Results

With regard to low-speed machines, the phase resistance of the winding (R_c) is the dominant factor affecting the fault's behavior, while the stator inductance is comparatively minor [26]. The reactance is increased with frequency in standard interturn fault models and thus becomes important at higher speeds; however, at lower rotational speeds, the current's fundamental and harmonic components are dependent on R_c rather than inductance. Moreover, lower back-EMF at reduced speeds does not cause significant fault-induced current anomalies and thus produces weaker fault indicators in the standard motor current spectrum. We can see in Tables III - IV that they align with the eq. 5 - 8. We know that $I_{Rcont} = I_a - I_f$ for this reason when R_{cont} decreases then I_{Rcont} decreases but because $I_f > I_a$ and therefore I_{Rcont} will be negative and it will increase as an absolute rms value. The same applies when the number of the shorted turns increases therefore we can see the same results as above. But, in case of $R_{cont} = 0$ the mutual inductance has greater impact giving us the opposite results. This is validated in Table V. By observing Tables III - V, the current of the shorted coil and the current of the contact

resistance have small values when the fault severity is low, as it can also be seen in Fig.5, meaning C-GEN has the potential to operate under ITSC.

Table III: Current of the healthy part of the SC-Coil

Nshorted \ Rcont	0.5 (ohm)	0.2 (ohm)	0 (ohm)
1	12.14 A	12.14 A	12.13 A
2	12.14 A	12.14 A	12.13 A
3	12.14 A	12.14 A	12.12 A
18	12.13 A	12.11 A	12.00 A

Table IV: ITSC Coil Current

Nshorted \ Rcont	0.5 (ohm)	0.2 (ohm)	0 (ohm)
1	12.61 A	13.31 A	87.35 A
2	13.08 A	14.44 A	87.01 A
3	13.53 A	15.52 A	86.66 A
18	19.36 A	27.78 A	81.17 A

Table V: Current of $R_{contact}$

Nshorted \ Rcont	0.5 (Ohm)	0.2 (Ohm)	0 (Ohm)
1	- 0.47 A	- 1.17 A	-75.22 A
2	- 0.93A	- 2.29 A	-74.88 A
3	- 1.39A	- 3.38 A	-74.54 A
18	- 7.24 A	- 15.68 A	-69.27 A

Figure 5: RMS current of an inter-turn shorted (ITSC) stator coil versus the contact resistance (R_{cont}) and the number of shorted turns (N). The coloured surface shows the measured fault currents; the translucent horizontal plane at 12.13 A marks the healthy-coil reference.

IV. CURRENT-BASED METHODS

A. MCSA

Small-scale short circuits are often cited as being effectively detectable using motor current signature analysis (MCSA), which is widely employed to identify inter-turn short-circuit (ITSC) faults in PMSGs [25]-[26]. In practice, such fault-induced signatures at low fault severity are often so subtle that MCSA has trouble distinguishing them from normal operating harmonics or measurement noise. And the rapid propagation of small ITSC faults to catastrophic failure complicates timely diagnosis. Thus, even though MCSA is still useful for moderate

or high-severity faults, relying exclusively on it for early-stage detection may result in missed detections ("false negatives") and highlight the need for additional approaches such as stray flux or torque-based monitoring to achieve full coverage. It can be seen from Table VI and Fig.6, that very low fault indication signatures appear. When, the fault severity is low the asymmetry that the fault induces can correct an existing asymmetry. Table VI: MCSA 3rd harmonic

Nshorted \ Rcont	0 (ohm)	0.2 (ohm)	0.5 (ohm)
1	-82.71 dB	-79.74 dB	-79.65 dB
2	-77.96 dB	-80.15 dB	-79.82 dB
3	-74.37 dB	-80.61 dB	-80.06 dB
18	-66.96 dB	-73.85 dB	-82.07 dB

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Figure 6: MCSA results for faulty cases (red $R_{cont} = 0$, magenta $R_{cont} = 0.2$, cyan $R_{cont} = 0.5$) versus the healthy (black) where: a) 1 shorted turn, b) 2 shorted turns, c) 3 shorted turns and d) 18 (20%) shorted turns.

B. EPVA

EPVA is known to lead to an increase of the dedicated signatures at multiples of double the supply frequency when inter-turn short circuit appear [27], practical measurements do not reveal a clear rise for incipient faults - when only some turns are shorted or when a nonzero contact resistance limits the short-circuit current. As shown in Table VII and Fig.7, the 2nd-harmonic levels remain close to the healthy values for low numbers of shorted turns (e.g., 1–3). While the signatures are more distinct than those of the MSCA, when the fault severity is low, the indication is still small. In case of the 4th harmonic we can see a rise only when we have 20% fault severity (18 turn) and $R_{cont} = 0$. Where the amplitude is -73.13 db which is 17.36 db rise from healthy. Although in theory EPVA can detect evolving stator winding faults, it may produce false negatives in practice for low-severity faults in which the short-circuit current and thus the 2x signature is suppressed by the resistance. This limitation shows why real-world incipient fault detection often requires additional or alternative strategies - even though EPVA has been useful in more pronounced cases like on-site tests in large industrial motors, as discussed in [28].

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Figure 7: EPVA results for faulty cases (red $R_{\text{cont}} = 0$, magenta $R_{\text{cont}} = 0.2$, cyan $R_{\text{cont}} = 0.5$) versus the healthy (black) where: a) 1 shorted turn, b) 2 shorted turns, c) 3 shorted turns and d) 18 (20%) shorted turns.

Table VII: EPVA 2^{nd} harmonic

Nshorted \ Rcont	0 (ohm) (dB)	0.2 (ohm) (dB)	0.5 (ohm) (dB)
1	-76.2 dB	-90.86 dB	-90.76 dB
2	-69.91 dB	-91.14 dB	-90.68 dB
3	-66.37 dB	-90.42 dB	-90.78 dB
18	-50.82 dB	-63.92 dB	-71.02 dB

CONCLUSION

This work demonstrates an original analytical investigation of inter-turn short-circuit behavior in dual-rotor, air-cored

PMSG with series-connected coils. The analytical findings are fully supported by FEA. Using a similar circuit formulation, with an explicit mutual-inductance term coupled to 3-D FEA, a cause-and-effect chain from the physical fault (number of shorted turns and contact resistance) to the resulting current redistribution and the weak spectral signatures observed in practice is obtained. The work shows that the fault is mainly governed by resistive effects at the very low fundamental frequencies of C-GEN machines: Even when 20% of the turns of a coil are short-circuited, their current sharply rises, while the phase-current harmonics are restrained. Such behavior explains why early-stage inter-turn short circuit (ITSC) faults go undetected by traditional current-based techniques.

Moreover, results show that both MCSA and EPVA change by less than 5 dB for up to three shorted turns when contact resistance is not zero. They reconcile previously conflicting reports in the literature and provide a lower bound on the sensitivity that can be reasonably expected of each method. Additionally, very low severity ITSCs may keep the generator within safe thermal and electromechanical limits.

To conclude, complementary strategies intergration could enhance the fault detection reliability. Future efforts should be focused in incorporation of transient and thermal effects, ensuring more robust and accurate diagnostics in renewable energy systems.

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APPENDIX

$$y = \frac{a \cdot x + b}{c \cdot x + d} \Rightarrow \frac{dy}{dx} = \frac{a \cdot (c \cdot x + d) - (a \cdot x + b) \cdot c}{(c \cdot x + d)^2} = \frac{a \cdot d - b \cdot c}{(c \cdot x + d)^2} \quad (9)$$

$$y = \frac{a \cdot x^2 + b \cdot x + c}{d \cdot x^2 + e \cdot x + f} \Rightarrow \frac{dy}{dx} = \frac{(2 \cdot a \cdot x + b)(d \cdot x^2 + e \cdot x + f) - (a \cdot x^2 + b \cdot x + c) \cdot (2 \cdot d \cdot x + e)}{(d \cdot x^2 + e \cdot x + f)^2} = \frac{(a \cdot e - b \cdot d) \cdot x^2 + 2 \cdot (a \cdot f - c \cdot d) \cdot x + b \cdot f - c \cdot e}{(d \cdot x^2 + e \cdot x + f)^2} \quad (10)$$